

Can A Divorced Wife Be Denied Maintenance On Proved Adultery? - An Evaluative Study

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Abstract

Marriage, as it stands now in India is a consensual and contractual relationship between a man and woman. It demands sexual exclusivity between husband and wife and if any of the spouses engage in extra-marital affair, marriage can be dissolved. However marriage is also a relationship of economic dependency. The reason why State is so vested in protecting marriage is because it delegates some of the society's collective responsibility for dependency to the family. This economic dependency right is guaranteed to wives in different personal laws and also under section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973. The obligation of a husband to maintain his wife arises from the anxiety of the legislature to protect deserted wives from the bitter necessity of earning a living by trading on their sex. That obligation however ceases when it has been voluntarily assumed by some man other than the woman's husband. The legal consequence of adultery is dissolution of marriage and not deprivation of maintenance. The divorced wife is economically dependent on the ex-husband and only for this purpose, law considers her a wife until she is remarried. Denial of maintenance to her on the ground of sexual purity is not only morally wrong but also a legal fallacy.

Introduction

Marriage, as it stands now in India is a consensual and contractual relationship between a man and woman. It demands sexual exclusivity between husband and wife and if any of the spouses engage in extra-marital affair, marriage can be dissolved. Adultery was once considered a crime but this position changed after the judgment of *Joseph Shine v. Union of India*¹. It is now treated only as a matrimonial offence for which the punitive action is dissolution of marriage as per respective personal laws. However marriage is also a relationship of economic dependency.

¹ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/42184625/>

The reason why State is so vested in protecting marriage is because it delegates some of the society's collective responsibility for dependency to the family. This economic dependency right is guaranteed to wives in different personal laws and also under section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973. This is a secular provision that grants maintenance to wife, children and parents of the husband with conditions attached.

Materials and methods:

Since the problem under study requires mostly doctrinal study and research, the material collected from primary and secondary sources. They include e-journals, case laws, annotations, and treatises. The primary sources are the Acts and the cases decided by the courts in India.

Analysis of the law on maintenance:

The Supreme Court in the case of *Captain Ramesh Chander Kaushal v. Mrs. Veena Kaushal & Others*² observed the constitutional basis for section 125. The court noted that it is a measure of social justice and specially enacted to protect the women and children and falls within the scope of Article 15(3) reinforced by Article 39. Article 15(3) gives authority to state to make special provisions for women and children while Article 39 embodies the concept of 'welfare state'. The objective is to prevent women from suffering destitution. Invoking the concept of 'constitutional empathy', Justice Krishna Iyer, in this case observed that if there are two interpretations of a section, the courts can be selective and chose that interpretation which advances the cause of the derelicts. It can therefore be said that section 125 can only be interpreted to guarantee the provision of maintenance to wife.

Section 125(1) stipulates that a wife can claim maintenance from husband if she is unable to maintain herself and the husband has the sufficient means to provide her the same. And for this purpose, the wife is defined in the explanation clause (b) of subsection (1) as a 'divorced' wife. Section 125 (4) states that "*No wife will be allowed to receive an allowance from her husband under this section if she lives in adultery, or if, without any sufficient reason, she refuses to live with her husband, or if they are living separately by mutual consent.*" Although the language of

² <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1861636/>

section 125 is very clear, the phrase ‘living in adultery’ in subsection (4) had been subjected to misinterpretation time and again. One such instance is the Madras High Court decision in *M. Chinna Karuppasamy v. Kanimozhi* (2015)³. It was held in this case that if the divorce was granted to the husband on the ground of adultery, wife cannot claim maintenance. The fallacy of this ruling lies in extending the disqualification of maintenance in section 125(4) to the ‘divorced wife’.

The Supreme Court had laid down the law regarding the same in *Smt. Vanamala v. Shri. H.M.Ranganatha Bhatta*⁴. In deciding the question whether a wife divorced by mutual consent is still eligible for maintenance under section 125(4), the court answered in the affirmative. The wife in clause (4) is a ‘married wife’ and not a divorced wife as the phrase used is ‘living in adultery’. Since after dissolution of marriage, there is no question of a divorced wife living in adultery. Hence the disqualification from maintenance is only in the case of a married wife living in adultery. Similarly there would be no question of divorced wife and husband living separately with mutual consent. This judicial reasoning was reiterated in *Rohtash Singh v. Ramendri*⁵. The Apex Court in this case upheld that section 125(4) is applicable only as long as marriage is subsisting and not where the marriage has ended. It is very clear from these precedents that the bar in section 125(4) is only applicable to the married wife living in adultery.

In spite of these binding precedents, the Bombay High Court in its latest order⁶ ruled that the aforementioned Supreme Court precedents are not relevant as the issue of maintenance in those cases was not based on the ground of proved adultery. The Court held that there is an expressed embargo in section 125(4) and hence a divorced wife cannot claim maintenance if adultery is proved. This interpretation of the section is not only erroneous but also sexist to say the least. To uphold that the divorced wife cannot claim maintenance since adultery was proved would imply that the ex-husband continues to have proprietary interest in the ex-wife in the sense of demanding sexual purity. Such an interpretation would invariably link chastity with economic dependency which is a blatant violation of the woman’s right to sexual autonomy intrinsic in Article 21.

³ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/193218875/>

⁴ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/585496/>

⁵ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1728416/>

⁶ https://www.livelaw.in/pdf_upload/pdf_upload-368402.pdf

This delinking of chastity from economic dependency can be well understood through a Madras High Court judgment of 1937. In *A.T.Lakshmi Ambalam v. Andiammal*⁷, the court observed “Now I understand the phrase “living in adultery” to mean something quite different from living an unchaste life. The principle, it seems to me, is that a husband is absolved from the obligation to maintain his wife when his wife has a de facto protector with whom she lives and by whom she is being maintained as if she were his wife. The obligation of a husband to maintain his wife arises from the anxiety of the legislature to protect deserted wives from the bitter necessity of earning a living by trading on their sex. That obligation however ceases when it has been voluntarily assumed by some man other than the woman’s husband. No woman can fairly claim a right to be kept by two men.” Undoubtedly, the language used here is deeply problematic. However this clearly establishes that economic welfare of the wife is the sole reason for maintenance in section 125 and chastity is irrelevant while granting this right.

Conclusion

The legal consequence of adultery is dissolution of marriage and not deprivation of maintenance. The divorced wife is economically dependent on the ex-husband and only for this purpose, law considers her a wife until she is remarried. Denial of maintenance to her on the ground of sexual purity is not only morally wrong but also a legal fallacy.

⁷ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1226760/>